

Solving State- Sponsored Impunity- A Modest Proposal For The United Nation Security Council to Create An International Tribunal to Adjudicate the Alleged War Crimes of the Nepalese Civil War

*Saurabh Sharma*¹

Abstract

Nepal's armed conflict (1996–2006) resulted in widespread violations of international human rights and humanitarian law, including torture, enforced disappearance, extrajudicial killing, and conflict-related sexual violence. Nearly two decades later, Nepal's transitional justice process remains unable to deliver effective investigation, prosecution, or reparations. Despite constitutional guarantees, Supreme Court rulings, and international treaty obligations, the Truth and Reconciliation Commission (TRC) and the Commission of Investigation on Enforced Disappeared Persons (CIEDP) have failed to complete even a single investigation or forward a case for prosecution across multiple reconstitutions from 2015 to 2025.

This article analyzes Nepal's domestic legal deficiencies, structural political interference, and security-sector non-cooperation, and evaluates the State's compliance with obligations under the ICCPR and customary international law. It further examines the 2022–2025 transitional justice amendment efforts, which continue to allow amnesties for violations that may constitute war crimes or crimes against humanity, contrary to international norms. Drawing on UN reports, case law, and comparative international tribunal practice, this article argues that Nepal meets the “unable or unwilling” threshold recognized in international criminal jurisprudence, thereby justifying external intervention. The paper concludes that a hybrid or internationalized tribunal mandated by the United Nations Security Council may be necessary to ensure justice, accountability, and durable peace.

Keywords: Nepal; Transitional Justice; Truth and Reconciliation Commission (TRC); Impunity; International Human Rights Law; ICCPR; Serious Human Rights Violations; United Nations Security Council (UNSC); Hybrid Tribunals; Accountability; Enforced Disappearance; Armed Conflict.

¹The Author is a Managing Law Clerk at The Dworsky Law Firm, Illinois, USA. He is a candidate for Executive MBA at Ottawa University, Kansas. He holds a B.A.LL.B. (Hons.) degree from Rajiv Gandhi National University of Law, Punjab, India and a Master of Laws(LL.M.) from Mississippi College School of Law, Mississippi, USA. The author can be reached at saurabhsharma9991@gmail.com

I. Introduction

Conflict and Its Impact

*“Leaders who are silent and do nothing are as guilty and do worse than those who commit these horrific attacks”.*²

-George Stamatīs

Conflict that led to the massive human rights and international humanitarian law violation, destruction of property and life of the civilians, broke out on 13 February 1996, when the government failed to respond a forty-point list demands presented by the Communist Party of Nepal (CPN-M).³ The conflict took the life of more than 13,000 people (including both civilians and armed forces). Throughout 1996-2005 Maoists killed 4,500 Nepalis and on the other side 8,200 Nepalis were killed by the government forces from 1996-2005.⁴ In addition, an estimated 100,000 to 150,000 people were internally displaced because of the conflict. The government forces were accused of arbitrary arrests, unlawful detentions, disappearances unlawful killing of civilians, torture including rape.⁵⁶ Human rights defenders, including lawyers; journalists and members of NGO's were arrested, tortured, killed or "disappeared" in Nepal.⁷ Nepal held the unique distinction for the highest number of "disappearances" of any country in 2003 and 2004.⁸ The Maoists have resorted to torture and deliberate and unlawful killings.⁹¹⁰ According to INSEC (Informal Sector Service Centre), a human rights organisation, nearly 3000 people were killed and about 26,000 people were abducted in 2004 in Nepal.¹¹ The Maoists abducted civilians, including teachers and schoolchildren for the purpose of 'political indoctrination'.¹² In April 2006, there was a country-wide people's movement in Nepal, popularly known as the Jana Andolan II,¹³ against King Gyanendra direct rule¹⁴ following a 12-point understanding reached between the Seven Party Alliance¹⁵ and the Communist Party of Nepal (Maoist), which was leading a communist insurgency

² George Stamatīs.

³ Sudheer Sharma, *The Maoist Movement: An Evolutionary Perspective*, in *Understanding the Maoist Movement of Nepal*, Deepak Thapa, ed. 361 (Kathmandu: Modern Printing Press, 2003). The forty-point memorandum, signed by Dr. Baburam Bhattarai, can be found in *Understanding the Maoist Movement of Nepal* at 391–95.

⁴ Ed Douglas, *Inside Nepal's Revolution*, *Nat'l Geographic Mag.*, Nov. 2005, at 54.

⁵ Amnesty Int'l, *Nepal: Killing with Impunity* (Jan. 20, 2004), <https://www.amnesty.org/en/documents/ASA31/001/2005/en/>

⁶ Amnesty International. Nepal Human Rights Defenders under threat. Amnesty International, London, UK; (28 July 2004) <http://www.web.amnesty.org/library/Index/ENGASA311412004>

⁷ Id.

⁸ Amnesty International. Nepal Fear for safety Fear of disappearance. Amnesty International, London, UK; (29 July 2004) <http://web.amnesty.org/library/Index/ENGASA311502004?open&of=ENG-NPL>.

⁹ Amnesty International. *Supra note at 4*.

¹⁰ Amnesty International. *Supra note at 7*.

¹¹ Informal Sector Serv. Ctr. (INSEC), *Human Rights Yearbook 2004* (Kathmandu: INSEC, 2005), <http://www.inseconline.org/hryb005.htm>

¹² Amnesty International. *Supra note at 4*.

¹³ Jana Andolan I being the people's movement against the three-decade-long Panchayat regime led by the king.

¹⁴ King Gyanendra had dismissed the civilian government on February 1, 2005, enforced what in effect was martial law after declaring a national emergency, curtailed all human, civic and political rights, and formed a government led by himself.

¹⁵ The Seven Party Alliance (SPA) comprised of the Nepali Congress, the mainstream Communist Party of Nepal (Unified Marxist-Leninist) and a number of other smaller parties, mainly leftist, including People's Front Nepal (PFN), Nepal Workers and Peasants Party (NWPP), Nepal Sadbhawana Party- (NSP-A) and United Left Front (ULF) led by CP Mainali

against the state. The 19-day-long Jana Andolan II¹⁶ (People’s Movement II) ended direct rule by Gyanendra, forced him to return power to the reinstated parliament, and created a conducive environment for the signing of the Comprehensive Peace Agreement (CPA) between the government and the rebel Maoists in November 2006. The success of Jana Andolan II in thus ending the decade-long conflict that had affected all parts of the country has thus been hailed by many as being exemplary of the ways in which engaged citizenry and communities at the local level can have an impact on the resolution and transformation of violent conflict at the national level.

This article therefore examines Nepal’s breach of its obligations under International Human Rights Law (IHRL) and International Humanitarian Law (IHL), focusing on two central failures: the State’s inability or unwillingness to hold perpetrators of wartime atrocities accountable, and its failure to ensure victims an effective remedy as required under both domestic and international legal frameworks. Building on these findings, the final section evaluates the duty of the United Nations Security Council to establish an ad hoc international tribunal to adjudicate the alleged war crimes should Nepal remain unable to deliver justice. It further analyzes the consequences of inaction and draws on historical precedent, such as the establishment of the ICTY and ICTR, to demonstrate the legal and institutional basis upon which the Security Council may intervene.

I.I Legal and Institutional Background

Nepal's transitional justice framework rests primarily on the Commission on Investigation of Disappeared Persons, Truth and Reconciliation Act of 2014 (“TRC Act”).¹⁷ The Act created two mechanisms: the Truth and Reconciliation Commission (TRC) and the Commission of Investigation on Enforced Disappeared Persons (CIEDP), both mandated to investigate conflict-era violations, recommend prosecutions, and propose reparations.¹⁸ However, from the beginning, the TRC Act contained several structural flaws that undermined its ability to deliver justice. The Act granted broad discretionary power to recommend amnesty even for violations such as torture and enforced disappearance, subject only to vague “public interest” language.¹⁹

In 2015, the Supreme Court of Nepal invalidated key provisions of the Act, holding that amnesty for gross human rights violations, including torture, disappearance, war crimes, and crimes against humanity, violated both the Constitution and Nepal’s obligations under the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights.²⁰ The Court ordered the government to amend the law, criminalize serious international crimes, guarantee victims’ rights, and ensure an independent prosecutorial process.²¹ Despite this, Nepal has not enacted legislation fully implementing the Court’s directives, and the TRC and CIEDP continue to operate under a framework inconsistent with domestic and international law.

Between 2015 and 2025, the commissions received nearly 80,000 complaints but failed to complete a single full investigation.²² Their inability to conduct credible inquiry stems from a

¹⁶ Jana Andolan I being the popular movement against the present king’s brother’s absolute rule in 1990.

¹⁷ Commission on Investigation of Disappeared Persons, *Truth and Reconciliation Act*, 2071 (2014) (Nepal).

¹⁸ *Id.* §§ 3–4.

¹⁹ *Id.* § 26.

²⁰ *Suman Adhikari v. Gov’t of Nepal*, N.K.P. 2071/72, Decision No. 070 (Sup. Ct. Nepal Feb. 26, 2015).

²¹ *Id.*

²² Int’l Comm’n of Jurists, *Nepal: Transitional Justice Mechanisms Require Legal Reform* (2017).

combination of inadequate investigative powers, lack of prosecutorial authority, shortages of forensic expertise, and persistent political interference.²³ The government's repeated extension of the commissions' terms, without providing adequate legal or institutional reforms, has resulted in prolonged stagnation and deep disillusionment among conflict victims.

I.II Domestic Legal Failures in Nepal's Transitional Justice Process

Nepal's transitional justice process has been undermined from the outset by structural flaws in its legal and institutional design. Although the Truth and Reconciliation Commission (TRC) and the Commission of Investigation on Enforced Disappeared Persons (CIEDP) were created to address serious human rights violations committed during the armed conflict, the domestic framework governing these institutions has repeatedly failed to comply with constitutional guarantees, Supreme Court jurisprudence, or Nepal's international legal obligations.

First, the Commission on Investigation of Disappeared Persons, Truth and Reconciliation Act of 2014 ("TRC Act") grants overly broad discretionary powers to the commissions, including the ability to recommend amnesty for grave violations such as torture and enforced disappearance.²⁴ This approach conflicts with Nepal's obligations under the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR), which prohibits amnesty for serious human rights violations.²⁵ The Supreme Court of Nepal recognized this inconsistency in its landmark 2015 decision in *Suman Adhikari v. Government of Nepal*, where it held that amnesty for grave violations violated both the Constitution of Nepal and Nepal's treaty obligations.²⁶ Despite this ruling, Parliament has repeatedly failed to enact legislation that fully implements the Court's directives.

Second, the commissions lack independent investigative and prosecutorial authority. The TRC and CIEDP cannot file criminal cases in court, compel cooperation from state security forces, or demand the disclosure of classified military or police documents.²⁷ As a result, even when the commissions identify potential perpetrators, they have no mechanism to initiate prosecution. This structural weakness has been criticized by the International Commission of Jurists, which noted that "Nepal's transitional justice mechanisms lack the independence, clarity, and authority required to conduct credible investigations."²⁸

Third, political interference remains pervasive. Successive governments have widely misused their authority to withdraw criminal cases involving politically connected perpetrators, including individuals accused of conflict-era torture, enforced disappearance, and extrajudicial killing.²⁹ The Attorney General's Office has, at times, invoked prosecutorial discretion to halt or decline investigations even when evidence supports prosecution. This pattern undermines both judicial independence and the rule of law.

²³ Human Rights Watch, *No Law, No Justice: Nepal's Transitional Justice Process Stalled* (2020).

²⁴ *Commission on Investigation of Disappeared Persons, Truth & Reconciliation Act, 2071* (2014) (Nepal) § 26.

²⁵ International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights arts. 2, 6–7, Dec. 16, 1966, 999 U.N.T.S. 171.

²⁶ *Suman Adhikari v. Government of Nepal*, N.K.P. 2071/72, Decision No. 070 (Sup. Ct. Nepal Feb. 26, 2015).

²⁷ Human Rights Watch, *No Law, No Justice: Nepal's Transitional Justice Process Stalled* (Apr. 2020).

²⁸ International Commission of Jurists, *Nepal: Transitional Justice Bill Fails to Meet International Standards* (2023).

²⁹ *Id.*; Human Rights Watch, *Nepal: Justice Remains Elusive 17 Years After Conflict Ends* (Feb. 3, 2023).

Fourth, chronic institutional deficiencies, including lack of funding, absence of regulations, minimal investigative staff, and no forensic capacity have prevented the TRC and CIEDP from conducting meaningful inquiry. By 2025, the commissions had registered nearly 80,000 complaints, yet no case had been fully investigated or transmitted for prosecution.³⁰ The UN Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights (OHCHR) has repeatedly raised concerns about Nepal's failure to equip the commissions with the tools necessary to fulfill their mandates.³¹

Finally, the government's legislative efforts between 2022 and 2024 did not address these core deficiencies. Instead, proposed amendments continued to allow amnesty for violations such as torture and other serious crimes, contradicting the Supreme Court's 2015 ruling and international standards.³² These legal and institutional deficits demonstrate that Nepal's domestic framework is fundamentally incapable of providing truth, justice, or reparations, and they justify considering international intervention.

This article examines the legal implications arising from Nepal's inability to deliver accountability for conflict-era violations under both International Human Rights Law (IHRL) and International Humanitarian Law (IHL). Despite repeated commitments, Nepal has not completed investigations or prosecutions leading to final, enforceable convictions for grave human rights violations, nor have the transitional justice bodies, the Truth and Reconciliation Commission (TRC) and the Commission of Investigation on Enforced Disappeared Persons (CIEDP), referred any cases for criminal prosecution. The article will analyze these institutional and legal shortcomings, assess Nepal's failure to provide an effective remedy as required under domestic and international law, and evaluate the corresponding authority and responsibility of the United Nations Security Council to establish an ad hoc international tribunal. The final section considers past instances in which the Security Council has created such tribunals and discusses the potential consequences of inaction in the Nepal context.

II. Nepal has breached International Human Rights Law and International Humanitarian Law by providing safe heavens to those responsible for the war crimes

*"Lost rights are never regained by appeals to the conscience of the usurpers, but by relentless struggle..... Goats are used for sacrificial offerings and not lions."*³³

-Bhimrao Ramji Ambedkar

II.I Accountability of Perpetrators of Gross Human Rights Violations

The deadliest war ended with a Comprehensive Peace Accord (hereinafter referred as C.P.A) signed between Maoist guerrillas and the Nepalese Government on November 21, 2006. One of the provisions in the Peace accord includes establishing a truth and reconciliation

³⁰ International Commission of Jurists, *Nepal: Transitional Justice Mechanisms Require Legal Reform* (2017).

³¹ Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, *Nepal: Transitional Justice Must Be Independent, Impartial and Victim-Centered* (Oct. 2021).

³² Amnesty International, *Nepal: Transitional Justice Amendments Must Prioritize Victims' Rights* (2022).

³³ Bhimrao Ramji Ambedkar

commission “to find facts about those involved in committing serious human rights violations and those involved in crime against humanity during the armed conflict.³⁴ In the Interim Constitution of Nepal 2063, the provision was made to identify and search the enforced disappeared people.³⁵ Under Article 33(c)³⁶ it imposes on the State an obligation to “*To adopt a political system fully upholding the universally accepted concepts of basic human rights, rule of law and accountability in the activities of political parties, public participation and impartial, efficient and fair bureaucracy, and to maintain good governance, while putting an end to corruption and impunity.*” The mockery of the state could be vividly seen on this provision. It was provisioned that the questions regarding the Directive principles and the state policy could not be questioned in the court.³⁷ This was the contradictory provision clearly visible.

For this, the systemic pattern of attempts surrounding accountability must be overlooked here. Since, the armed conflict that happened between 2052 BS to 2063 in Nepal satisfies the *Tadic test* as propounded by the landmark case of International Criminal Tribunal for Yugoslavia (ICTY) for a non-international armed conflict: the involvement of an organized armed group, and the intensity of violence.³⁸ Nepal as a state and the subsequent government after the Comprehensive Peace Agreement is responsible under the Common Article 3, found in Geneva Conventions I–IV, is a cornerstone of jus cogens,³⁹ constituting a mini-convention that establishes fundamental protections applicable in all armed conflicts⁴⁰ of which Nepal is also responsible. In the case of Rajendra Dhakal⁴¹, the responsibility of the state to prosecute the human rights aggressor under Treaty Act, 2047 cannot be escaped. The constitution drafting committee failed in the process of drafting constitution through constituent assembly to align with the legal principles that in the case of armed conflict and war crimes, the act with the retrospective effect could be made. This was considered to be the procedural hurdle.

On October 22, 2005, there was an agreement between the seven political parties in Nepal and the then Maoists to defend democracy, protect the nation and nationalism, and accept the multi-party system by opposing the autocratic monarchy.⁴² With the 19 years struggle, known as Jana Andolan II, king restored the parliament dismissed by him. The same parliament based on the political compromise decided to overthrow the monarchy and introduce republican democracy. With the intent to incorporate Maoist into the peace making process, the Comprehensive Peace Accord between the then government led by Girija Prasad Koirala and the then insurgent led by Pushpa Kamal Dahal (Prachanda) which had two objectives in crux: **(a) social transformation** and **(b) conflict management**. The heart of the comprehensive peace accord lies in its clause which mentions⁴³ “*Both sides agree to set up with mutual consent a High-level Truth and Reconciliation Commission in order to probe into those involved in serious violation of human rights and crime against humanity in course of the armed conflict for creating an atmosphere for reconciliation in the society*”.

³⁴ *Comprehensive Peace Accord* pmb. & art. 5.2.5 (Nepal 2006).

³⁵ *Interim Constitution of Nepal 2063* (2007), pt. 4.

³⁶ *Id.* art. 33(c).

³⁷ *Interim Constitution of Nepal 2063* (2007), art. 36(1).

³⁸ Anthony Cullen, *The Concept of Non-International Armed Conflict in International Humanitarian Law* (Cambridge Univ. Press 2010).

³⁹ Dietrich Schindler, *The Different Types of Armed Conflicts According to the Geneva Conventions and Protocols*, 163 *Recueil des Cours* 131, 151 (1979).

⁴⁰ *Military and Paramilitary Activities in and Against Nicaragua (Nicar. v. U.S.) (Merits)*, 1986 I.C.J. 14, 218.

⁴¹ *Rajendra Dhakal et al. v. Ministry of Home Affairs*, Decision No. 7817 (Sup. Ct. Nepal [2064]).

⁴² T.N. Ghimire, *Nepali Sanghatmat Byabastha Awadharana ra Auchitya* (Pinakal Publ'g 2022).

⁴³ *Comprehensive Peace Accord* art. 5.2.5 (Nepal 2006).

The truth vs. justice debate has balanced the merits of trials against other accountability mechanisms. The 1990s in particular were marked by this dichotomy, due to the almost simultaneous creation of the South African Truth and Reconciliation Commission (TRC) and the ICTY, which became emblematic of this discussion.⁴⁴ Truth commissions have been promoted as alternatives to prosecutions and as important mechanisms for counteracting cultures of denial. It has been argued that public and official exposure of truth provides redress for victims and may contribute to individual and social healing and reconciliation.⁴⁵ Divided societies in particular need truth-seeking and truth-telling mechanisms. Given that nationalist myth-making, based on historical distortion, has fuelled both interstate and intrastate wars, efforts to prevent the instrumentalization of facts and history are needed to prevent a return to violent conflict.⁴⁶

As the discourse has moved on, many more authors agree that societies recovering from oppression or violent conflict need both legal and restorative approaches, addressing different levels and dimensions of truth and justice. Alexander Boraine (former member of the South African TRC and founder of the International Centre for Transitional Justice, ICTJ) has made an important contribution to this discussion by suggesting that retributive justice should be complemented with restorative justice. He strongly advocates a holistic interpretation based on five key pillars, including accountability, truth recovery, reparations, institutional reform and reconciliation.⁴⁷

Accountability derives from the fact that no society can claim to be free or democratic without strict adherence to the rule of law; there are mass atrocities and crimes that have been so devastating that civilisation cannot tolerate their being ignored. Yet in cases of large-scale human rights violations such as in the former Yugoslavia, Rwanda or Sierra Leone, it is impossible to prosecute everyone. Given the limits to the law and prosecution, and although criminal justice is important, additional activities are needed that focus on documenting the truth about the past. Within truth recovery, four different notions are covered: objective or forensic truth (evidence and facts about human rights violations and missing persons), narrative truth (storytelling by victims and perpetrators and communicating personal truths and multi-layered experiences to a wider public), social or dialogical truth (truth of experience that is established by interaction, discussion and debate) and healing or restorative truth (documentation of facts and acknowledgement to give dignity to the victims and survivors). Reparations play an important role, as they belong to the few efforts undertaken directly on behalf of the victims. Nevertheless, reparations need to be closely connected to other processes aiming at documenting and acknowledging truth; otherwise they could be interpreted as being insincere. Institutional reforms form a prerequisite for truth and reconciliation. There has been criticism that in many cases truth commissions have chosen to focus almost entirely on individual hearings. Instead, Boraine argues, they need to focus on institutional settings in order to call to account those institutions directly responsible for the breakdown of a state, repression or human rights violations.⁴⁸

⁴⁴ Pierre Hazan, *Measuring the Impact of Punishment and Forgiveness: A Framework for Evaluating Transitional Justice*, 88 *Int'l Rev. Red Cross* 861, 19–47 (2006).

⁴⁵ Priscilla Hayner, *Fifteen Truth Commissions, 1974–1994: A Comparative Study*, 16 *Hum. Rts. Q.* 597, 597–655 (1994).

⁴⁶ David Mendeloff, *Truth-Seeking, Truth-Telling, and Post-Conflict Peacebuilding: Curb the Enthusiasm?*, 6 *Int'l Stud. Rev.* 355, 355–80 (2004).

⁴⁷ Alexander Boraine, *Transitional Justice: A Holistic Interpretation*, 60 *J. Int'l Aff.* 17, 17–27 (2006).

⁴⁸ B. Austin, M. Fischer & H.J. Giessmann, eds., *Advancing Conflict Transformation: The Berghof Handbook II* (Barbara Budrich Publ'rs 2011), available at www.berghof-handbook.net

In the context of Nepal, the TRC Act empowers both the commissions to enquire and investigate into the truth about the incidents of the gross violations of human rights and the crime against humanity in the course of the armed conflict and about those who were involved in those incidents, create an environment of sustainable peace and reconciliation by enhancing the spirit of mutual trust and tolerance upon bringing about reconciliation in the society, and to make recommendation for legal action against those who were involved in grave offences relating to those incidents including for reparation to the victims of those incidents.⁴⁹ The Supreme Court of Nepal struck down the provision and required serious crimes to be prosecuted. The Supreme Court further observed that many crimes such as torture, disappearance, war crime, crimes against humanity also needed to be criminalized under Nepali penal law.⁵⁰ The Supreme Court of Nepal has also, from time to time, rendered decisions which have evolved victim-friendly judicial principles.⁵¹ This is the evidence that the Nepal expected to achieve justice through reconciliation and also punishing the perpetrator. From the legislative instruments that Nepal drafted to ensure transitional justice, it is my finding that Nepal has embodied two models: **(a) Amnesty and Reconciliation Models** and **(b) Prosecution Models**.

But in contrary, Nepal's transitional justice process has consistently sidelined the specific experiences, needs, and voices of victims.⁵² Despite the global institutionalization of transitional justice rhetoric, this discourse often loses its transformative edge in practice. As Hazan (2004, p. 19) notes, "*Transitional justice has become the new mantra of domestic and international politics since the end of the Cold War.*"⁵³ Yet in Nepal, this rhetoric has repeatedly been co-opted as a tool for elite political compromise rather than a pathway to meaningful accountability. Transitional justice processes are rarely neutral; they are frequently shaped by political negotiations and unequal power structures that sideline the lived experiences of victims, particularly of women and structurally marginalized communities (Robins, 2012). Since the signing of the Comprehensive Peace Accord in 2006, Nepal's transitional justice institutions the TRC and CIEDP have operated under political expediency rather than transformative justice, consistently prioritizing elite political bargains and state stabilization over the rights of victims.⁵⁴ Former Chief Justice and International Commission of Jurists (ICJ) Commissioner Kalyan Shrestha critically remarked,

*"If we pride ourselves on a home grown transitional justice process, the billion-dollar question is: what does home-grown mean, if politics is placed above justice?"*⁵⁵

His words resonate even more deeply in a context where victims voices have been consistently sidelined raising the question of whether this process can claim legitimacy if it fails to reflect the perspectives and needs of half the population. His comment underscores the ongoing tension between state-led political imperatives and victim-centered justice demands in Nepal.

⁴⁹ *Truth and Reconciliation Commission Act 2071* (2014) (Nepal) pmbl. & § 10.

⁵⁰ *Madhav Kumar Basnet v. Gov't of Nepal*, Order No. 069-WS-0058 (Sup. Ct. Nepal)

⁵¹ *Suman Adhikari v. Gov't of Nepal*, Order No. 070-WS-0050 (Sup. Ct. Nepal)

⁵² NSEC & UPR Info., *Summary Report: Victim Consultation for Nepal's UPR Fourth Cycle Preparation* [unpublished internal document] (June 2025) (on file with INSEC).

⁵³ Pierre Hazan, *Measuring the Impact of Punishment and Forgiveness: A Framework for Evaluating Transitional Justice*, 88 *Int'l Rev. Red Cross* 19, 19–47 (2006), <https://doi.org/10.1017/s1816383106000038>

⁵⁴ P.D. Greiff, *The Applicability of Transitional Justice in Pre-Conflict Contexts* (Pathfinders 2021).

⁵⁵ Int'l Comm'n of Jurists, *Nepal: Prime Minister Oli and Political Leaders Commit to a Victim-Centered Transitional Justice Process* (2024),

<https://www.icj.org/nepal-prime-minister-oli-and-political-leaders-commit-to-a-victim-centred-transitional-justice-process/>

The ICJ also raised similar concerns and recommended that the Government of Nepal should amend the Bill.⁵⁶ In August 2024, both houses of Nepal's Parliament passed, and the President promulgated, the *Third Amendment to the Disappeared Persons' Enquiry, Truth and Reconciliation Commission Act 2014* ("Amended TRC Act").⁵⁷ The predecessor of the TRC Act, the TRC Act of 2014, fell short of Nepal's Constitution, and the country's international law obligations. Responding to a writ filed by conflict victims, the Supreme Court (SC) in 2015 declared that some provisions of the 2014 legislation including those allowing an amnesty for serious crimes; and those concerning mediation between victims and alleged perpetrators irrespective of the nature of crimes and without the victims' consent undermined judicial independence and rendered of the 2014 Act unconstitutional. In its 2015 ruling the SC confirmed that the abovementioned provisions of the 2014 Act violated both Nepal's international legal obligations and earlier rulings of the Court.⁵⁸

Thus, The Act (third amendment) tries to bring all major violations under the mandates of the Truth and Reconciliation Commission (TRC) and of the Commission of Investigation on Enforced Disappearances Persons (CIEDP). It classifies human rights violations that took place during the conflict into two categories: '*violations of human rights*'⁵⁹ and '*serious violations of human rights*'.⁶⁰ This classification is crucial as it determines the legal pathway for seeking redress and the types of remedies that are available. "Violations of human rights" are defined as "any act, except serious violations of human rights, committed in contravention of existing Nepali law, international human rights, or humanitarian law during the armed conflict by the parties involved, targeting unarmed individuals or communities, or committed in a planned manner."⁶¹ "Serious violations of human rights" are defined as "rape or other forms of serious sexual violence, "intentional or arbitrary killing", "enforced disappearances (where the whereabouts of the person remain still unknown)" and "inhuman or cruel torture," targeting 'unarmed individuals or communities, or committed in a "planned manner".⁶² While the bifurcation into "violations of human rights" and "serious violations of human rights" under the TRC/CIEDP mandate represents a formal achievement bringing many conflict era abuses within the purview of transitional justice mechanisms it simultaneously exposes important shortcomings. The classification suffers from conceptual ambiguity: by limiting "serious violations" to only rape or serious sexual violence, arbitrary or intentional killing, enforced disappearance (where the person's fate remains unknown), and inhuman or cruel torture, the law excludes other grave crimes under international law. This leaves a loophole for many serious abuses to be treated as mere "violations" rather than prosecutable offenses, which in practice could permit those acts to be granted amnesty, thereby undermining victims' access to full justice. The Act prohibits the granting of an amnesty for "serious violations of human rights," but allows it under certain conditions in cases of "violations of human rights". With respect to amnesties for perpetrators of "violations of human rights", the Act sets out the following conditions that must be met for perpetrators to be eligible to an amnesty although it is unclear whether fulfilment of simply one or all of these conditions is

⁵⁶ Int'l Comm'n of Jurists & Human Rights Watch, *Nepal's Proposed Law Disregards Domestic and International Legal Standards* (Mar. 23, 2023),

<https://www.icj.org/nepal-transitional-justice-bill-needs-to-protect-victims-not-abusers/>

⁵⁷ Bill adopted by the House of Representatives on Aug. 14, 2024, and by the National Assembly on Aug. 22, 2024, available at <http://rajpatra.dop.gov.np/welcome/book/?ref=25706>

⁵⁸ *Suman Adhikari & Others v. Gov't of Nepal & Others*, Decision No. 9303, Nepal Law Journal 2071, Vol. 12 (Feb. 27, 2015) (Nepal).

⁵⁹ *Truth and Reconciliation Commission (Third Amendment) Act 2071* (2014) (Nepal) § 2(j).

⁶⁰ *Id.* § 2(j1).

⁶¹ *Id.* § 2(j).

⁶² *Id.* § 2(j1)

required.⁶³ Under international law amnesties cannot be granted for war crimes, crimes against humanity, genocide or torture. Furthermore, the duty under international law to provide redress renders amnesties unlawful in respect of other gross violations of human rights.⁶⁴

The South African TRC has been the only truth commission to grant amnesties, using a truth-for-amnesty formula. It adopted a very specific model to facilitate this process. The legislation which created the TRC established a “Committee on Amnesty” which, unlike other parts of the TRC, was a quasi-judicial body that was chaired by a judge who presided over the proceedings, testimony, and cross-examination. The amnesty committee was entrusted with the task of evaluating whether the regulation’s specific conditions for amnesty had been fulfilled and thereby whether amnesty should be granted or refused. Amnesties were therefore not automatic, but conditional. The amnesty committee could only grant an amnesty if it was satisfied that the applicant had made a full disclosure of all relevant facts, and that the act was associated with a political objective and was proportionate to this objective. A total of 7,112 applications for amnesty were filed, and the process of reviewing each was slow due in part to the quasi-judicial nature of the proceedings.⁶⁵ Ultimately, 5,392 applicants were refused and only 849 were granted amnesty. The Office of High Commissioner for Human Rights has stated that it is doubtful whether the South Africa TRC amnesty provisions would be found acceptable by international human rights bodies if they were implemented today.⁶⁶ Several other truth commissions have been provided with a mandate that included the ability to recommend rather than provide amnesties, provided that no recommendation is given for serious violations of international humanitarian law, crimes against humanity, and gross human rights violations. The Liberian TRC could recommend amnesty in the event the persons applying provided “full disclosures of their wrongs and thereby expressing remorse for their acts and/or omissions, whether as an accomplice or a perpetrator, provided that amnesty or exoneration shall not apply to violations of international humanitarian law and crimes against humanity in conformity with international laws and standards.⁶⁷ Kenya’s Truth, Justice and Reconciliation Commission is also able to receive applications for amnesty and recommend the granting of amnesty for acts provided that “they do not qualify as a gross violation of human rights.

Under the Amended TRC Act, if the TRC or CIEDP uncovers evidence of “serious violations of human rights”, the case must be referred to the Attorney General for legal action, denoting prosecution. In addition, the Amended TRC Act provides the establishment of a three-member Special Court to try and resolve⁶⁸ cases involving “serious violations of human rights” referred to it by the Attorney General or public prosecutor authorized by the Attorney General.⁶⁹ Under the Amended TRC Act, appeals against the Special Court’s decisions, such

⁶³ Id. § 26

⁶⁴ U.N. Human Rights Council, *Basic Principles and Guidelines on the Right to a Remedy and Reparation for Victims of Gross Violations of International Human Rights Law and Serious Violations of International Humanitarian Law*, U.N. Doc. A/RES/60/147 (Dec. 16, 2005); see also OHCHR, *Rule-of-Law Tools for Post-Conflict States: Amnesties* 20–21 (U.N. 2009, New York & Geneva).

⁶⁵ John Dugard, *Reconciliation and Justice: The South African Experience*, 5 *Transitional L. & Contemporary Probs.* 1 (1998).

⁶⁶ OHCHR, *Rule-of-Law Tools for Post-Conflict States: Amnesties* 33 (U.N. 2009, New York & Geneva) (stating “it is doubtful whether it would survive scrutiny under the legal standards developed by such bodies as the Human Rights Committee and the Inter-American Commission on and Court of Human Rights”).

⁶⁷ *An Act to Establish the Truth and Reconciliation Commission (TRC) of Liberia*, s. 26(g) (enacted May 12, 2005).

⁶⁸ *Truth and Reconciliation Commission (Third Amendment) Act 2071* (2014) (Nepal) § 29a(1).

⁶⁹ Id. §§ 29(3)–(4)

as convictions and acquittals, will be heard by a designated joint bench of transitional justice in the Supreme Court, whose justices will be selected by the Chief Justice.⁷⁰

Nepal has refrained from its positive obligation to secure human rights and negative obligation to refrain from violating them. Amnesties are impermissible if they: [A] prevent prosecution of individuals who may be criminally responsible for war crimes, crimes against humanity or gross violations of human rights, [B] interfere with the victims' right to an effective remedy, including reparations and [C] Restrict victims and societies' right to know the truth about the violations of human rights and humanitarian law.⁷¹ According to Geneva Convention I, State parties undertake to enact any legislation necessary to provide effective penal sanction for persons committing, or ordering to be committed shall bring such persons before its own courts. An amnesty to prevent prosecution of war crimes is the direct violation of the state's obligation under customary law.⁷²

Institutionally, the TRC has been repeatedly condemned by civil society, victims' groups, and international observers. The first-term commissions, constituted in 2015, operated under a flawed legal framework that ignored Supreme Court directives and international human rights obligations. Despite receiving more than 60,000 complaints, the TRC failed to conduct a single full investigation. Rape and sexual violence victims were excluded from interim relief, and female staff were virtually absent in local peace committees. The second-term commissions, reconstituted in 2020, again failed to establish legitimacy or deliver outcomes. Political parties continued to control appointments, and victims' networks expressed frustration over the opaque processes and unfulfilled mandates.⁷³ In mid-2025, a third set of commissioners, including TRC Chairperson Mahesh Thapa and CIEDP Chairperson Lila Devi Gadtaula, were appointed⁷⁴ through a politically dominated process, without meaningful victim participation.⁷⁵

The Act provides that the tenure of the TRC and the CIEDP members will be four years.⁷⁶ The Amended TRC Act requires that the victims of conflict-related sexual violence (CRSV), who have previously not registered their cases with the Commission, will have a three-month window for a onetime to do so.⁷⁷ The TRC and CIEDP, established under the TRC Act of 2014, had already collected complaints from victims (the TRC has recorded 60316 complaints while the CIEDP has registered 3288 cases).⁷⁸ However, many victims, especially of CRSV, had refused to register their case with the TRC. Their reluctance stemmed from multiple factors, including the stigma attached to sexual violence, concerns about confidentiality, and a deep mistrust of the Commissions, which were perceived to be operating under flawed provisions. Nearly four months after the appointment of a new five-member team led by Mahesh Thapa, Nepal's Truth and Reconciliation Commission (TRC) continues to face significant delays due to the lack of approved regulations, an

⁷⁰ Id. § 29e(2)

⁷¹ D.J. Harris, M. O'Boyle, E.P. Bates & C.M. Buckley, *Law of the European Convention on Human Rights* 21–22 (Oxford Univ. Press 2014).

⁷² UNHCR, *Rule-of-Law Tools for Post-Conflict States: Amnesties* 12 (2009).

⁷³ Human Rights Watch, *Nepal: Transitional Justice Proving Elusive* (Feb. 13, 2018), <https://www.hrw.org/news/2018/02/13/nepal-transitional-justice-proving-elusive>

⁷⁴ Conflict Victims Society, *Statement on the Appointments to TRC and CIEDP* (May 16, 2025).

⁷⁵ M. Bhatta, *What Next for Nepal's Transitional Justice Process?*, *The Diplomat* (Aug. 2024), <https://thediplomat.com/2024/08/what-next-for-nepals-transitional-justice-process/>

⁷⁶ *Truth and Reconciliation Commission (Third Amendment) Act 2071* (2014) (Nepal) § 38(1).

⁷⁷ *Truth and Reconciliation Commission (Third Amendment) Act 2071* (2014) (Nepal) § 13(6a).

⁷⁸ *TRC and CIEDP Remains Without Office Bearer for a Year*, *Republica* (Aug. 17, 2023), <https://myrepublica.nagariknetwork.com/news/trc-and-ciedp-remain-without-office-bearers-for-a-year>

organization and management (O&M) survey, and a finalized four-year strategy, hindering staff appointments and planning.⁷⁹

Despite having laws the government failed to hold individuals accountable for their abuses during the war. Frequent changes in the government and weak enforcement of laws, corruption and political will, all commitments made by the government are in vain. It's been more than a decade, and no one has been criminally prosecuted in a court for serious human rights violations. The reason for all this is the lack of appropriate legislation where the laws doesn't give proper definition of the offences and doesn't provide penalties for those offences committed. "In addition, the immunity granted to police and army under the various acts stated that no case should be filed against army personnel for acts undertaken in the course of duty that result in death or loss suffered by any person."⁸⁰ But later in 2006 the Army Act amended the provision, preserving immunity for the acts that result in death or loss, committed "in good faith".⁸¹ The Police and Armed Police Force Acts also grant immunity to Nepal Police and Armed Police Force employees who act with "good intention" while discharging duties.⁸² In addition Terrorist and Disruptive Activities Act/Ordinance provided immunity from punishment act conducted in a good faith.⁸³ These vague laws and government unwillingness to charge those with political connections provided them with a shield from prosecution makes it hard for the civilians to get justice.

II.II The ridicule of self-amnesty: People with Political Connections are likely to have their cases withdrew

The term 'self-amnesties' denotes 'amnesties given by a government to itself and its allies for crimes directly attributable to them.'⁸⁴ Blanket, and general and self-protecting amnesties, is unacceptable. International law unequivocally prohibits this kind of amnesties, and the vast body of literature overwhelmingly confirm this position.⁸⁵ Blanket, general and self-protecting amnesties lead to the defencelessness of victims and perpetuate impunity; they preclude the identification of the perpetrators by obstructing the investigation and access to justice; they prevent the victims and their relatives from knowing the truth and receiving the appropriate reparation⁸⁶, they are inconsistent with the general principles of law forbidding self-judging; and therefore, the positive effect that they permit a military regime to abandon its grip over the state, they are not regarded with a high degree of mistrust. Examples of such unacceptable amnesties can be found in Chile (1978), El Salvador (1993), Peru (1995), and Sierra Leone (1999), where the Special Court for Sierra Leone in the famous case Kallon and Kamarra, the Court has considered the amnesty without effect since it is, inter alia, "contrary to the direction in which customary international law is developing and to the obligations in certain treaties and conventions the purpose of which is to protect humanity".⁸⁷

⁷⁹ *Truth Commission Lacks Tools to Act Amid Rising War-Era Complaints*, Kathmandu Post (Sept. 7, 2025), <https://kathmandupost.com/national/2025/09/07/nepal-truth-panel-lacks-tools-to-act-amid-rising-complaints>

⁸⁰ *Army Act* 1959 (Nepal) § 24A.

⁸¹ *Army Act* 2006 (Nepal) § 22.

⁸² *Police Act* (Nepal) § 37; *Armed Police Force Act* (Nepal) § 26; *Armed Police Force Regulation* (Nepal) R. 83(1).

⁸³ *Terrorist and Disruptive Activities (Control and Punishment) Act/Ordinance* (Nepal) § 20.

⁸⁴ Mark Freeman, *Necessary Evils: Amnesties and the Search for Justice* (Cambridge Univ. Press 2010).

⁸⁵ M. Cherif Bassiouni, *International Criminal Law* 10 (2d ed. 1990).

⁸⁶ *Barrios Altos v. Peru*, Judgment, C. Ser. No. 75, Inter-Am. Ct. H.R. (Mar. 14, 2001) 48.

⁸⁷ *Prosecutor v. Kallon & Kamara*, App. Decision, SCSL-2004-15/AR72(E) & SCSL-2004-16/AR72(E), ¶¶ 71, 73, 84, 88 (S.C.S.L. Mar. 13, 2001).

The Nepal TRC Bill uses the term reconciliation, which is "melmilap" in Nepali, but does not provide a definition of what reconciliation means. Melmilap can be translated as “a settlement” so does not necessarily capture the full meaning of reconciliation. Moreover, the drafting of the reconciliation provision in the TRC Bill is troubling. It is unclear how any TRC could cause reconciliation “to be made.” Reconciliation is both a personal and a social process that may or may not occur over a long time period and cannot be crystallized into a single, formalized event. While uncovering the truth, providing reparations, ensuring criminal accountability of perpetrators, or implementing institutional reforms may in different ways contribute to reconciliation, it is difficult to imagine that a truth commission can definitively reconcile victims and perpetrators, although it may be helpful in stimulating reconciliation.

The transitional justice framework in Nepal, particularly the TRC Bill, is deeply intertwined with the political settlement forged under the Comprehensive Peace Agreement (CPA) of 2006. This agreement, reached between the Maoists and the then-government, was primarily a political compromise to end the decade-long armed conflict, ensure integration of combatants, and maintain political stability. Consequently, many of the principal perpetrators of conflict-era violations are closely linked to the political actors who negotiated and shaped the CPA. By granting the same actors the authority to design and oversee mechanisms of justice, Nepal effectively institutionalizes self-amnesty, where perpetrators or their allies have the power to influence the investigative and adjudicative processes. This arrangement undermines the independence of the justice mechanism and erodes the credibility of transitional justice in the eyes of victims, civil society, and the international community.⁸⁸

At its core, natural justice requires that justice processes be fair, impartial, and free from bias, ensuring that no one is a judge in their own case. The Nepal TRC framework violates this principle because the very individuals or political groups responsible for past atrocities are implicated in shaping the legal definitions, procedures, and discretionary powers of the commission. By allowing those connected to the conflict and implicated in serious violations to influence decisions about amnesty, investigation, and reconciliation, the process becomes inherently conflicted. The result is a structural incompatibility with the universal principles of impartiality and fairness: a mechanism designed to deliver accountability cannot credibly function when its architects are politically or personally linked to the acts under scrutiny. This structural compromise generates an accountability gap that can be analyzed through the **doctrine of the poisonous tree**, a principle in law stating that evidence or justice derived from a tainted source is itself tainted and unreliable. In the Nepalese context, the “roots” of the transitional justice system are politically compromised: those who negotiated the CPA, maintained positions of authority, and are linked to the perpetrators effectively control or influence the mechanisms of accountability. Consequently, any findings, amnesties, or reconciliation measures originating from this system risk being fundamentally biased or illegitimate. If the root of justice is compromised, the fruits whether reports, prosecutions, or reparations cannot be regarded as fair or credible.

To substantiate the critics cited above, in the past years, after the war came to an end, government have withdrawn hundreds of criminal cases against individuals accused of serious offences including Murder,⁸⁹ citing the CPA which called for withdrawal of cases

⁸⁸ Int’l Comm’n of Jurists & Human Rights Watch, *Nepal’s Proposed Law Disregards Domestic and International Legal Standards* (Mar. 23, 2023),

<https://www.icj.org/nepal-transitional-justice-bill-needs-to-protect-victims-not-abusers/>

⁸⁹ Nat’l Hum. Rts. Comm’n of Nepal & Office of the U.N. High Comm’r for Human Rights, *Remedies and Rights Revoked: Case Withdrawals for Serious Crimes in Nepal, Legal Opinion* (June 2011), http://nepal.ohchr.org/en/resources/publications/2011/2011_06_23_Case-Withdrawals-for-Serious-Crimes-in-Nepal_E

brought against individuals “due to political reasons.”⁹⁰ Around 349 cases were registered out of which, half of the total cases slated for withdrawal by the UCPN(M)-led government in 2008 were for murder or attempted murder.⁹¹ On the other hand, the another Communist Party of Nepal (United Marxist Leninist (UML))- led government withdrew cases against another 282 individuals; 200 of them charged with murder and 82 with arson.⁹²

In September 2011 a four-point agreement signed between the UCPN(M) and the United Democratic Madheshi⁹³ Front (UDMF) prior to the election of Baburam Bhattarai as Prime Minister, extended case withdrawals to a variety of other political actors such as Maoists, members of the Madheshi, Janajati, Tharuhat, Dalit, and Pichadabarga movements.⁹⁴ By the end of December 2011, the government of Prime Minister Baburam Bhattarai had reportedly prepared a list of 130 individuals accused of involvement in of serious crimes, including murder, arson, and robbery, whose cases it planned to withdraw.⁹⁵ Since then there have been other withdrawals of criminal cases against individuals with political affiliations. There were media reports that the UCPN(M)-led government decided to withdraw cases against 425 individuals in March 2012. These included cases of murder, attempted murder and abduction.⁹⁶

In April 2012 the Court reportedly ordered the government and the Bara District court in Nepal’s Terai region not to withdraw serious cases, even if they were of political nature. The court also directed the government to amend provisions in the Working Procedure and Criteria for Withdrawing Criminal Cases 1998 to make sure that cases related to "serious crimes," listed in media reports as including treason, war crimes, crimes against humanity and serious human rights abuses were not withdrawn. The order came in response to a writ filed in July 2010 challenging the withdrawal of a criminal case against a man accused of murdering five people in January 2010 in Bara district.⁹⁷

II.III Protection from Prosecution

In case of Major Niranjan Basnet, who was facing an arrest warrant for the murder of 15-year-old Maina Sunuwar (tortured to death by security forces after her arrest in 2004) was returned to Nepal from peacekeeping duties in Chad in December 2009, the Nepal Army (NA) openly defied a court order and refused to hand him over to the police. Six months later

⁹⁰ *Comprehensive Peace Agreement* between the Gov’t of Nepal and the Communist Party of Nepal (Maoist), Nov. 21, 2006, cl. 5.2.7.

⁹¹ Remedies and Rights Revoked.

⁹² Advocacy Forum (AF) et al., *Nepal Descending Towards Full-Spectrum Impunity for Human Rights Abuses Committed During the Conflict: Open Letter to the Government and Political Leaders of Nepal on the Occasion of International Human Rights Day 2010* (Dec. 10, 2010) (Index: ASA 31/003/2010), <http://www.amnesty.org/en/library/asset/ASA31/003/2010/en/0c1d3d55-f2fb-4828-b9d3-a15da585c0a7/asa310032010en>

⁹³ Madhesh is another term for the Terai region of Nepal.

⁹⁴ Asian Human Rights Comm’n, *Nepal: Plan to Withdraw Criminal Cases Is a Serious Blow to the Rule of Law* (Sept. 14, 2011), <http://www.humanrights.asia/news/ahrcnews/AHRC-STM-119-2011>

⁹⁵ *Govt Prepares to Withdraw Court Cases Against 130*, *Ekantipur.com* (Dec. 24, 2011), <http://www.ekantipur.com/2011/12/24/top-story/govt-prepares-to-withdraw-court-cases-against-130/346051.html>

⁹⁶ *Parties in Agreement on Criminal Case Withdrawals*, *Republica* (Mar. 6, 2012), http://www.myrepublica.com/portal/index.php?action=news_details&news_id=32530

⁹⁷ *SC to Govt: Don’t Withdraw Serious Criminal Cases*, *Kathmandu Post* (Apr. 17, 2012), <http://www.ekantipur.com/the-kathmandu-post/2012/04/17/top-story/sc-to-govt-dont-withdraw-serious-criminal-cases/233872.html>

in June 2010 the army announced that a military inquiry, which was neither independent nor impartial, and conducted its proceedings in secret, had found him innocent of the charges.

In the Case of, Agni Sapkota, former Minister and Constituent Assembly member, currently serves as the UCPN(M) party spokesperson. In 2008 the Supreme Court ordered the police to file a criminal complaint against his alleged involvement in the abduction and killing of school teacher Arjun Lama, in Kavre district in April 2005.⁹⁸ The subsequent police investigation has been inadequate, despite the Supreme Court ordering progress reports from the Kavre Police every 15 days.⁹⁹ In June 2012, according to a press report, records at the Office of the Attorney General showed that police in Kavre had been filing their reports only once a month and noted little progress in their investigation, stating that police had been unable to locate Sapkota; despite his very public profile.¹⁰⁰ On 27 July 2012, the government ordered the investigation into the killing of Arjun Lama to be suspended. However, on 26 November 2012, the Supreme Court ordered that the investigation should continue subject to its final decision on the suspension.

II.IV Promoting the Alleged Perpetrators of the War Crimes

UN Commission on Human Rights in its resolution on impunity which was adopted without a vote in 2002, recognized that perpetrators of war crimes should be prosecuted or extradited.¹⁰¹ In cases of Sierra Leone, the Republic of Chechnya of the Russian Federation, Rwanda, Sudan, Burundi and former Yugoslavia, the Commission adopted resolutions and most of them were without a vote which required the investigation and prosecution of persons alleged to have violated IHL. It is now considered as a customary international legal obligation to investigate and prosecute the alleged perpetrator of IHL violations, either in international or non-international armed conflict.¹⁰²

UN has developed the guidelines on how to conduct investigations, the guidelines have four principles, which are Independence, effectiveness, promptness and impartiality. These principles lie at the heart of human rights protection and are binding on the UN members in they have been relied upon and further develop in the jurisprudence of UN-backed international courts and have been agreed upon by the States represented within the relevant United Nations bodies.¹⁰³

Further, UN Human Rights Committee has repeatedly held that the failure to investigate and punish perpetrators of IHRL violations constitute a separate violation of ICCPR. Committee in the case of *Bautista de Arellana v. Colombia*, ruled that Colombia was under a duty to

⁹⁸ Amnesty Int'l, Int'l Comm'n of Jurists & Human Rights Watch, *Open Letter to the Prime Minister of Nepal Regarding Persistent Impunity in Nepal* (May 24, 2011) (Index: ASA 31/003/2011), <http://www.amnesty.org/en/library/asset/ASA31/003/2011/en/9d07cfbd-ae24-4ae0-a219-911b031bf465/asa310032011en.pdf>

⁹⁹Sup. Ct., Div. Bench, Hon. Justices Ramkumar Prasad Sah & Prakash Osti, Order, Writ No. 1094 of the Year 2068 (Nepal); Supreme Court of Nepal, Division Bench, Hon. Justices Ramkumar Prasad Sah & Prakash Osti, Order, Writ No. 1094 of the Year 2068.

¹⁰⁰ *Murder Slur on Sapkota: Police Probe Makes No Headway*, *Ekantipur.com* (June 25, 2012), <http://www.ekantipur.com/2012/06/25/top-story/murder-slur-on-sapkota-police-probe-makes-no-headway/356118.html>

¹⁰¹ U.N. Comm'n on Hum. Rts., Res. 2002/79, 11 (2002).

¹⁰² Int'l Comm. of the Red Cross, *Customary International Humanitarian Law* (Rule 158).

¹⁰³ U.N. Econ. & Soc. Council, *Principles on the Effective Prevention and Investigation of Extra-Legal, Arbitrary, and Summary Executions*, Res. 1989/65, annex, available at <https://www1.umn.edu/humanrts/instreet/i7pepi.html>

investigate allegations of forced disappearances and to criminally prosecute those responsible for such violations.¹⁰⁴

Nepal has also failed to abide by the obligation imposed by the international law when the government promoted the Raju Basnet,¹⁰⁵ where Supreme Court of Nepal on 83 habeas petitions, recalled the state's obligations under Nepal's Constitution and international law to investigate and prosecute allegations of enforced disappearances. It named Bhairabnath Battalion and individual officers serving in that Battalion, including Colonel Raju Basnet as alleged perpetrators.¹⁰⁶ The Supreme Court subsequently halted his promotion in a stay order issued on 15 October 2012.

Similarly, in '**Dhanusha Five case**, where Five male students (Sanjiv Kumar Karna, Durgesh Kumar Labh, Jitendra Jha, Shailendra Yadav, and Pramod Narayan Mandal) were forcibly disappeared and appear to have been killed in Nepal's Dhanusha district 2003, Witnesses say the young men were arrested by a joint army-police operation on 8 October 2003, near Janakpur municipality in Dhanusha District. Kuber Singh Rana was Chief of Police in Dhanusha district at the time of the incident. On January 29, 2008, the NHRC submitted a letter to Nepal's Prime Minister and Council of Ministers outlining the results of its investigation into the case, identifying Kuber Singh Rana and other members of the security forces they believed were responsible for arresting the five victims; noting that the army claimed the victims were killed by the police, while police alleged they were turned over to the army; and calling for prosecution of perpetrators and compensation of victims and their dependents. The NHRC issued a press release summarizing its findings on 30 January 2008.¹⁰⁷ On 3 February 2009 the Supreme Court ordered police to investigate Kuber Singh Rana and others' involvement in the enforced disappearance. Exhumations carried out by the Nepal Police with NHRC and foreign assistance between September 2010 and February 2011 found five male bodies, blindfolded and shot summarily, buried near a river bank, but the results of DNA tests are unknown. On 12 July 2011 the Supreme Court issued an interim order directing the Prime Minister to provide monthly reports to the Court and NHRC on the progress of the investigations.¹⁰⁸ In August 2012 the Supreme Court directed the Government of Nepal to establish vetting guidelines to prevent people implicated in human rights violations from holding public office. The order was ignored.

Corruption and Impunity is a longstanding problem in Nepal, lack of political will to held account for past and present actions of the people with political connections is compounded by the obstacles to justice. It is very hard for the victims and their families to go against the alleged perpetrator with political connections. Victims or their families are scared to lodge a complaint because of the threat they receive from the alleged perpetrators. Change in policy

¹⁰⁴ Human Rights Comm., *Bautista de Arellana v. Colombia*, Comm. No. 563/1993, 8.6 (Oct. 27, 1995); *José Vicente and Amado Villafañe Chaparro, Luis Napoleón Torres Crespo, Angel María Torres Arroyo and Antonio Hugues Chaparro Torres v. Colombia*, Comm. No. 612/1995, 8.8 (July 29, 1995); *Rajapakse v. Sri Lanka*, Comm. No. 1250/2004, 9.3 (July 14, 2006).

¹⁰⁵ Amnesty Int'l, Int'l Comm'n of Jurists & Human Rights Watch, *Nepal: Promotion of War Crimes Suspect Affront to Justice* (Oct. 6, 2012) (Index: PRE 01/47/474/2012), <http://www.amnesty.org/en/for-media/press-releases/nepal-promotion-warcrimes-suspect-affront-justice-2012-10-06>

¹⁰⁶ *Rajendra Dhakal et al. v. Government of Nepal, Ministry of Home Affairs et al.*, Supreme Ct. Nepal (June 1, 2007).

¹⁰⁷ "The decision of the Commission Over the incidents of Janakpur and Kotvada, January 30, 2008," National Human Rights Commission of Nepal.

¹⁰⁸ Sup. Ct., Joint Bench, Hon. Justices Tahir Ali Ansari & Bharat Bahadur Karki, Order, Writ No. 067 (2010), W 1198 (July 13, 2011), <http://www.advocacyforum.org/downloads/sc-decision-in-kuber-rana-case.pdf>

to protect the criminals, weak enforcement of laws and corruption in the administration makes it harder for the victims to get justice.

Thus, the metaphor of a “safe haven for perpetrators” aptly captures the current state of transitional justice in Nepal, not because the legal framework is entirely silent, but because legislative inefficiencies and institutional weaknesses have rendered it largely ineffective. Repeated delays in implementing the TRC and CIEDP, unapproved regulations, vacant staff positions, and politically compromised appointments have collectively fostered an environment where perpetrators of conflict-era crimes continue to evade accountability. This persistent dysfunction perpetuates a culture of impunity, undermines victims’ trust in the justice system, and highlights that without robust legal enforcement and functional institutions; even well-intentioned laws remain powerless to deliver justice.

III. Nepal has failed to provide effective remedy to the victims of war crime

III.I. Right to an Effective Remedy and Reparation for Victims of Gross Human Rights Violations

Nepal is a party to International Human Rights Treaty; therefore, Nepal has an obligation to respect and ensure remedy and reparation to the individuals who either suffered physical harm or Mental injury because of the deadliest conflict. It is the duty of the state to provide effective relief as soon as individual rights have been violated. Including those remedies provided to them by the Constitution and other domestic laws. It is also the duty of the state to investigate and prosecute alleged perpetrator. Under Article 32¹⁰⁹ of Interim Constitution which gives right to constitutional remedy for those whose fundamental rights have been violated.

III.I.I. Remedy and Reparation Under International Organs

The right to a remedy and reparation for international crimes and human rights violations has been affirmed by a range of treaties,¹¹⁰ United Nations Treaty bodies,¹¹¹ regional courts,¹¹² and in a series of declarative instruments such as in Article 8 of Universal Declaration of Human Rights which states:

Everyone has the right to an effective remedy by the competent national tribunals for

¹⁰⁹ *Interim Constitution of Nepal* 2007, arts. 32, 107.

¹¹⁰ International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, arts. 2(3), 9(5), 14(6), Dec. 16, 1966, 999 U.N.T.S. 171; Convention Against Torture and Other Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment, art. 14, Dec. 10, 1984, 1465 U.N.T.S. 85; Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court, art. 75, Jul. 17, 1998, 2187 U.N.T.S. 90.

¹¹¹ H.R. Comm., *General Comment No. 31*, ¶¶ 15–17; U.N. Comm. Against Torture, *General Comment No. 2: Implementation of Article 2 by States Parties*, CAT/C/GC/2/CRP.1/Rev.4 (2007) 15..

¹¹² I.A. Ct. H.R., *Velásquez Rodríguez v. Honduras*, Judgment (July 29, 1988) 174; Eur. Ct. H.R., *Papamichalopoulos v. Greece*, App. No. 14556/89 (1995) 36.

*acts violating the fundamental rights granted him by the constitution or by law.*¹¹³

Right is also protected under Article 2(3) of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR)¹¹⁴, which states:

- a) *Ensure that any person whose rights or freedoms as herein recognized are violated shall have an effective remedy, notwithstanding that the violation has been committed by persons acting in an official capacity;*
- b) *Ensure that any person claiming such a remedy shall have his right thereto determined by competent judicial, administrative or legislative authorities, or by any other competent authority provided for by the legal system of the State, and to develop the possibilities of judicial remedy;*
- c) *Ensure that the competent authorities shall enforce such remedies when granted.*

Rights recognized under the Covenant can be effectively assured by the judiciary in many ways, including direct applicability of the Covenant, application of comparable constitutional or other provisions of law, or the interpretive effect of the Covenant in application of national law. In addition, it requires the allegation of violations are promptly, thoroughly and effectively investigated through independent and impartial bodies.¹¹⁵

It is the obligation of States not only to ensure right to an effective remedy but also to protect individuals from the private parties. There may be circumstances where rights have been violated because, either State is permitting or failing to take appropriate measures or to exercise due diligence to prevent, punish, investigate or redress the harm caused by such acts by private parties or entities. State Parties make reparation to individuals whose Covenant rights have been violated. Without reparation to individuals whose Covenant rights have been violated, the obligation to provide an effective remedy is not discharged. Moreover, when remedies are provided they must still be effective in practice and function according to the legal systems of the States.¹¹⁶

Before obligation to investigate, prosecute and punish, it should be understood that transitional justice has its own peculiar way of redress that the perpetrator should reinsure the public trust through the following manner:

III.I.II. Truth-Speaking

One of the most important forms of reparation is the search for and the acknowledgement of truth, but also of responsibility and indeed fault. In this sense, it is intrinsically linked to the right to an investigation and the right to truth. The UN Principles on Reparation list as measures of satisfaction the “verification of the facts and full and public disclosure of the truth to the extent that such disclosure does not cause further harm or threaten the safety and interests of the victim, the victim’s relatives, witnesses, or persons who have intervened to assist the victim or prevent the occurrence of further violations”, the “search for the

¹¹³Basic Principles on the Right to a Remedy and Reparation for Victims of Gross Violations of International Human Rights Law and Serious Violations of International Humanitarian Law, supra note __; U.N. Gen. Assembly, *Declaration of Basic Principles of Justice for Victims of Crime and Abuse of Power*, Res. 40/34 (Nov. 29, 1985); *Universal Declaration of Human Rights*, art. 8, G.A. Res. 217A (III), U.N. Doc. A/810 (1948).

¹¹⁴International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, art. 2(3), Dec. 16, 1966, 999 U.N.T.S. 171.

¹¹⁵ Human Rights Comm., *General Comment No. 31*, 15 (2004).

¹¹⁶ Id. ¶¶ 8, 16, 20.

whereabouts of the disappeared, for the identities of the children abducted, for the bodies of those killed, and assistance in the recovery, identification and reburial of the bodies in accordance with the with the expressed or presumed wish of the victims, or the cultural practices of the families and communities”; “public apology, including acknowledgement of the facts and acceptance of responsibility”, and “inclusion of an accurate account of the violations that occurred in international human rights and humanitarian law training and in educational material at all levels”.¹¹⁷ The search for, the acknowledgment and the publication of the truth and the recognition of responsibility are indeed forms of moral, non-monetary reparation and thus of satisfaction. Beyond the right to investigation and truth, public acknowledgement, apology and acceptance of responsibility are important forms of reparation. Along these lines, the UN Updated Principles on Impunity recommend that the final report of truth commissions be made public in full.¹¹⁸ Nonetheless, the punishment of the authors of the violation is a form of satisfaction.

III.I.III. Guarantees of non-repetition

Whereas the obligation of cessation requires little interpretation, guarantees of non-repetition may take such diverse forms that there is a considerable body of jurisprudence indicating the different measures to be taken by States in order to ensure that similar violations to those found will not occur in the future, including the duty to adopt legislative measures to prevent further violations. The jurisprudence and practice has been classified in the UN Principles on Remedy and Reparation as encompassing, amongst others, measures such as ensuring civilian control over military and security forces, strengthening the independence of the judiciary, protection of legal, medical, media and related personnel and human rights defenders, and human rights training.¹¹⁹

III.I.IV. Obligation to Investigate, Prosecute and Punish

“In cases of gross violations of international human rights law and serious violations of international humanitarian law constituting crimes under international law, States have the duty to investigate and, if there is sufficient evidence, the duty to submit to prosecution the person allegedly responsible for the violations and, if found guilty, the duty to punish her or him.”¹²⁰

Most Crimes of concerns to the international community must not go unpunished and that their effective prosecution must be by enhancing international community. International crimes such as Genocide, Crime Against Humanity and War Crimes as reflected in the preamble of Rome Statute consider these crimes as a part of customary law and put an obligation on the state as their duty to prosecute crimes.¹²¹ Any violations recognized as criminal under domestic or international law, for example- Torture, Cruel Inhuman or

¹¹⁷U.N., *Basic Principles on the Right to a Remedy and Reparation for Victims of Gross Violations of International Human Rights Law and Serious Violations of International Humanitarian Law*, Principles 22(b), (c), (e), (h).

¹¹⁸Id. Principle 13.

¹¹⁹ Id. Principle 23.

¹²⁰ Id. Principle 4.

¹²¹Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court, Preamble, July 1, 2002, 2187 U.N.T.S. 90.

degrading treatment, arbitrary killing, and enforced disappearance or of similar nature. State parties to the ICCPR, which Nepal under this convention has an obligation to ensure that those responsible for gross violation of human rights must be brought to justice. Convention has also focused on when the public officials or state agents have committed violations of the Covenant rights, the state parties may not relieve perpetrators from personal responsibility, as has occurred with certain amnesties and prior legal immunities and indemnities.¹²²

Failure to investigate, failure to bring to justice perpetrators of such violations could in and of itself give rise to a separate breach of the Covenant.¹²³

One of the good example of where government failed to comply with the Supreme Court decision is where CPN (Maoist Center) leader Balkrishna Dhungel, who had been sentenced to life imprisonment by the Supreme Court of Nepal for murder of Ujjan Shrestha of Okhaldhunga on 24 June 1998. The Cabinet recommended presidential clemency for him and he was pardoned and released from Dillibazaar prison on 29 May 2018.¹²⁴

In the case of Sharma v. Nepal,¹²⁵ involving the disappearance and presumed death of the petitioner's husband at the hands of security forces, the Human Rights Committee found the Government of Nepal to have violated the victim's right to liberty and the prohibition on torture or cruel, inhuman or degrading treatment – each in conjunction with the right to an effective remedy.¹²⁶ It is notable the Human Rights Committee also found the petitioner herself to have been a victim of cruel, inhuman or degrading treatment, due to the anguish and stress caused by the Government's failure to investigate and clarify the fate of her husband.¹²⁷

Other requirements can be found in International Humanitarian Law. As summarised by the Customary IHL Rules which says that individuals are criminally responsible for war crimes they commit.¹²⁸ Further, it goes on to say that Commanders and other superiors are criminally responsible for war crimes committed by their subordinates if they knew, or had reason to know, that the subordinates were about to commit or were committing such crimes and did not take all necessary and reasonable measures in their power to prevent their commission, or if such crimes had been committed, to punish the persons responsible.¹²⁹ States must investigate war crimes allegedly committed by their nationals or armed forces, or on their territory, and if appropriate, prosecute the suspects.¹³⁰

The resolutions of the Human Rights Commission on impunity emphasize the importance of combating impunity and the importance to hold accountable perpetrators, including their accomplices, of violations of international human rights and humanitarian law. It recognizes that amnesties should not be granted to those who commit violations of international humanitarian and human rights law that constitute serious crimes and urges States to take

¹²² Human Rights Comm., *General Comment No. 31*, 18 (2004); *General Comment No. 20*, 44 (1992).

¹²³ Human Rights Comm., *General Comment No. 31*, 18 (2004).

¹²⁴ <https://kathmandupost.ekantipur.com/news/2018-05-29/murder-convict-dhungel-gets-presidential-pardon.html>

¹²⁵ *Yasoda Sharma v. Nepal*, Comm. No. 1469/2006, CCPR/C/94/D/1469/2006 (2008).

¹²⁶ *Supra* Note 122. 8. Violations were found with respect to ICCPR, arts. 7, 9, and 10, each read in conjunction with art. 2(3). The Human Rights Committee also observed that enforced disappearances constitute a violation of (or grave threat to) the right to life (art. 6), but did not adopt a finding with respect to the presumed death of the complainant's husband, in the absence of an adequate investigation (*Id.* ¶¶ 7.4, 7.8).

¹²⁷ *Id.* 7.9.

¹²⁸ Int'l Comm. of the Red Cross, *Customary International Humanitarian Law*, Rule 151.

¹²⁹ *Id.* Rule 153.

¹³⁰ *Id.* Rule 158.

action in accordance with their obligations under international law.¹³¹ Further, the Human Rights Committee has developed jurisprudence on the duty to prosecute and punish violations of human rights since its first individual cases concerning Uruguay. For example, in the case of *Bleier v Uruguay the Human Rights Committee* urged the Government “to bring to justice any persons found to be responsible for his death, disappearance or ill-treatment”.¹³² It considers that a climate of impunity for human rights violations (for example through amnesties) constitutes a breach of the obligations of States under the Covenant.¹³³

As, I discussed above, the withdrawal of cases of those with political connection just to protect them from criminal accountability involving serious crimes denies victims their right to an effective remedy, and consequently denies them the human rights that the Government is obligated to respect and ensure human rights, which Nepal Government has failed to do.

IV. United Nation Security Council has a duty to create International Tribunal to adjudicate the alleged war crimes of the Nepalese civil war

With the end of the WWII, there was a sense of understanding developed between the international community that there’s a need of an organization which would regulate international community just to avoid such type of future war from happening. So, United Nations was established in October 1945, with a hope to maintain international peace and security among the member states. “The purpose of the UN Charter is to maintain international peace and security, and to that end: to take effective collective measures for the prevention and removal of threats to the peace, and for the suppression of acts of aggression or other breaches of the peace, and to bring about by peaceful means, and in conformity with the principles of justice and international law, adjustment or settlement of international disputes or situations which might lead to a breach of the peace”.¹³⁴

Nepal being member of United Nation¹³⁵ has breached the International Law. It’s been more than a decade now after the war came to an end and no one has ever been tried before the court which clearly shows that Nepal is not willing and unable to solve this problem. In 2015, two war crimes commissions were established - one to probe enforced disappearances and the other to investigate other serious abuses. Since then they have collected over 60,000 complaints of violations from victims’ families and survivors. As the law previously stood, the commissions had no clear path to compel criminal trials, resulting in de facto amnesty. Even after the 2024 amendment formally allows ‘serious violations of human rights’ to be referred to a Special Court and bars amnesty for that category, the Special Court has not yet been constituted and no case has been forwarded for prosecution. In practice, therefore, perpetrators still enjoy de facto impunity.¹³⁶ Therefore, United Nation Security Council under UN Charter has a duty to adjudicate matter and bring justice to the perpetrator of a war crime.

¹³¹ U.N. Comm’n on Hum. Rts., Res. 2003/72, ¶¶ 2, 10; Res. 2002/79, ¶¶ 2, 11; Res. 2001/70, ¶ 2; Res. 2000/68, ¶ 4; E/CN.4/RES/1999/34, ¶ 4; Res. 1998/53, ¶ 4.

¹³² *Bleier v. Uruguay*, Comm’n No. 30/1978, U.N. Hum. Rts. Comm., ¶ 11, U.N. Doc. CCPR/C/15/D/30/1978 (1982).

¹³³ Human Rights Committee, Concluding Observations: Uruguay, ¶ 7, U.N. Doc. CCPR/C/79/Add.19 (1993).

¹³⁴ U.N. Charter art. 1..

¹³⁵ Admission to the UN on Dec/14/1955.

¹³⁶ <https://www.reuters.com/article/us-nepal-rights-warcrimes/nepal-victims-despair-despite-new-governments-pl-edge-over-war-crimes-idUSKCN1GA046>

International criminal law in the past has been adjudicated before the domestic courts. Domestic courts played a primary role in prosecuting international crimes.¹³⁷ Many international crimes have been codified immediately after the WWII. In addition to a codification, two International Military Tribunal (Nuremberg Tribunal and Tokyo Tribunal) were established to prosecute superior level German and Japanese military and civilian's authorities for crimes committed in context of war.¹³⁸ The tribunals were created by the agreement between four victorious powers: France, the Soviet Union, the United Kingdom, and the United States.¹³⁹

In the modern era the United Nation Security Council being the only institution of UN that can

1. authorize the use of force (outside of measures taken in self-defence)¹⁴⁰ and
2. Make determinations that are binding on states regardless of their direct consent or other treaty obligations.¹⁴¹

Chapter VII of the Charter deals with actions with respect to threats to the peace, breaches of the peace and acts of aggression and Article 39 states that:

The Security Council shall determine the existence of any threat to the peace, breach of the peace, or act of aggression and shall make recommendations or decide what measures shall be taken to maintain or restore international peace and security¹⁴². Decisions adopted by the Security Council are mandatory for all States, as established by Article 25¹⁴³. By signing and ratifying the Charter, UN Member States agree to accept and enforce them. That obligation is further stressed in Article 48: —

1. The action required carrying out the decisions of the Security Council for the maintenance of international peace and security shall be taken by all the Members of the United Nations or by some of them, as the Security Council may determine.
2. Such decisions shall be carried out by the Members of the United Nations directly and through their action in the appropriate international agencies of which they are members"¹⁴⁴ Nepal being an active member of the United Nation is obliged by any determination made by the Security Council whether or not she gives consent to it.

The International Criminal Tribunals are UN subsidiary organs established by the Security Council to exercise judicial functions which the Council itself does not possess the competence to exercise.¹⁴⁵ The Security Council does not possess the competence to determine individual cases of criminal liability. As such, the Council has not delegated to the Tribunals the performance of its own functions but rather those powers that are necessary for

¹³⁷ Beth Van Schaack & Ronald C. Slye, *International Criminal Law and Its Enforcement* 29 (2d ed. 2010).

¹³⁸ Id. at 30.

¹³⁹ Id.

¹⁴⁰ U.N. Charter art. 41; Christian Henderson, The Centrality of the United Nations Security Council in the Legal Regime Governing the Use of Force, in *Research Handbook on International Conflict and Security Law* 120, 123–24 (Nigel D. White & Christian Henderson eds., 2013); Benedetto Conforti & Carlo Focarelli, *The Law and Practice of the United Nations* 259–61 (4th ed. 2010).

¹⁴¹ U.N. Charter arts. 24, 103.

¹⁴² U.N. Charter art. 39.

¹⁴³ Id. Article 25.

¹⁴⁴ Id. Article 48.

¹⁴⁵ D. Sarooshi, "The Legal Framework Governing United Nations Subsidiary Organs", *BYIL* 67 (1996), 413 (428).

the exercise of their designated judicial functions. The exercise of these functions by the Tribunals does not detract, however, from the legal position, that as UN subsidiary organs they are an integral part of the United Nations.¹⁴⁶ The Council has established the Tribunals as a measure that is necessary for the restoration and maintenance of international peace and security.¹⁴⁷ Reiterating the case of Tadic " "The Security Council has resorted to the establishment of a judicial organ in the form of an international criminal tribunal as an instrument for the exercise of its own principal function of the maintenance of peace and security, i.e., as a measure contributing to the restoration and maintenance of peace in the former Yugoslavia." Moreover, as the Secretary-General in his report to the Security Council on the establishment of the Tribunal states: "the International Tribunal should be established by a decision of the Security Council on the basis of Chapter VII. Such a decision would constitute a measure to maintain or restore international peace (the establishment of the Tribunal would be justifiable) in terms of the object and purpose of the decision (to maintain or restore international peace. The delegated mandate of the Tribunals has been stipulated by the Security Council in their respective statutes. Accordingly, the content of the powers, express or implied that the Tribunals can exercise is determined by reference to their statutes. This is not, however, the only source of powers of the Tribunals. They also possess certain inherent powers by virtue of their status as judicial bodies. The doctrine of implied powers is well accepted under international law. It was recognized in express terms by the ICJ as early as 1949 in the Reparation for Injuries Suffered in the Service of the United Nations Case where the Court stated: "Under international law the organization must be deemed to have those powers which, though not expressly provided in the Charter, are conferred upon it by necessary implication as being essential to the performance of its duties. The rights and duties of an entity such as the Organization must depend upon its purposes and functions as specified or implicit in its constituent documents and developed in practice.

However, translating this theoretical authority into practical action for Nepal is deeply challenging. First, political will is likely the biggest hurdle: for a Chapter VII referral or resolution mandating a tribunal, there must be consensus (or at least sufficient support) among the Security Council's permanent members. Nepal's geopolitical positioning and relationships with major powers may reduce the likelihood of such a referral. Second, Nepal already has a domestic mechanism its Special Court and transitional justice commissions, which complicates the complementarity argument: the Council would need to justify intervention by demonstrating that Nepal is *unwilling or unable* genuinely to try serious international crimes. Evidence strongly supports that case: human rights groups (HRW, ICJ) have repeatedly documented gaps in Nepal's transitional justice law, political interference, weak institutional capacity, and even amnesty provisions.

Still, a tribunal could be justified under the **complementarity principle**: Nepal's failure to prosecute conflict-era crimes credibly may satisfy the threshold for a UNSC tribunal, because the domestic system appears both structurally compromised and politically constrained. This tribunal would not necessarily supplant Nepal's institutions but could **complement** them, providing an impartial, international forum for accountability and offering victims a credible path to justice. Yet significant risks remain: a tribunal imposed externally could be perceived as infringing Nepal's sovereignty, generate legitimacy challenges among Nepali stakeholders, and require substantial and sustained international funding, infrastructure, and political backing.

¹⁴⁶ Id. 414.

¹⁴⁷ Prosecutor v. Tadić, Case No. IT-94-1-AR72, Decision on the Defence Motion for Interlocutory Appeal on Jurisdiction, 38 (Int'l Crim. Trib. for the Former Yugoslavia Oct. 2, 1995), 35 I.L.M. 32 (1996).

Therefore, while the Security Council has both the legal power and precedent to create a tribunal for Nepal, doing so now would require not just legal justification but also a carefully designed mandate that ensures local legitimacy, adequate institutional support, and robust protection for victims and witnesses. Without those, a tribunal risks being either symbolic or undermined by the same political dynamics that have plagued Nepal's domestic transitional justice process.

IV.I. Conflict in Nepal was similar to those situations in countries where UNSC Created an Ad Hoc Tribunals to Adjudicate the matter of International crimes

During the Nepal conflict, more than 13,000 civilians were killed. Both sides were involved in unlawful killings, extortion, torture, enforced disappearance, sexual violence, arbitrary arrest etc. And decade after the war ended, the perpetrators of a crime are roaming freely, this is due to impotence at the military and political levels which was one of the reasons for establishment of Ad Hoc tribunal in Yugoslavia. The Security Council established the ICTY in its Resolution 827 of 25 May 1993.¹⁴⁸ The reason for this resolution was that the Security Council determined that the situation in the former Yugoslavia, mainly in Bosnia and Herzegovina, where there were 'reports of mass killings, massive, organised and systematic detention and rape of women and the practice of "ethnic cleansing"- constitute a threat to international peace and security under Chapter VII of the UN Charter.¹⁴⁹ The proposal for the establishment of the ad hoc Tribunal was preceded by a number of UN statements proclaiming the principle that the authors of grave breaches of the Geneva Conventions and other crimes were 'individually responsible' and would be called to account.¹⁵⁰

The Security Council in November 1994 in its Resolution 955 established ICTR, in order to judge people responsible for the Rwanda genocide and other serious violations of international law between 1 January and 31 December 1994.¹⁵¹ The founding of the Rwandan Tribunal was influenced by the ICTY. Like the ICTY, the ICTR was established under the auspices of Chapter VII powers. The Security Council deemed the situation in Rwanda to "constitute a threat to international peace and security".¹⁵² The similarity between Nepal and Rwanda situation except for the international crimes, in Rwanda tribunal was implemented after the killings had ended and war in Nepal ended in 2006. So, the Security Council can still implement the tribunal in Nepal.

Other Courts such as Mixed Courts are the result of shortcoming affecting both domestic and international criminal courts in prosecuting international crimes. Generally, it is the primary responsibilities of the state to ensure arrest and prosecution of suspects, enforcement of criminal sentences. But sometimes national courts faced problem prosecuting international crimes, because some states are not developed enough to handle the situation and provide safety to those involved in the trial such as judges, prosecutors, defence, witnesses etc. and even if they are capable of prosecuting international crimes, state government might not be

¹⁴⁸ Antonio Cassese, *International Criminal Law* 337 (2d ed. 2003) (noting the drafting history of the ICTY Statute and citing S/25704 (May 3, 1993) and S.C. Res. 808, U.N. Doc. S/RES/808 (1993)).

¹⁴⁹ Id. at 337–38 (discussing S.C. Res. 827, U.N. Doc. S/RES/827 (1993) (establishing the ICTY), as amended by S.C. Res. 1166, U.N. Doc. S/RES/1166 (1998); noting amendments to the ICTR Statute in S.C. Res. 1165, U.N. Doc. S/RES/1165 (1998)).

¹⁵⁰ Id. at 336 (noting early proposals for an international tribunal, including statements by Robert Badinter, Dr. Klaus Kinkel, Roland Dumas, Elie Wiesel, and US Secretary of State Lawrence Eagleburger; citing UN Doc. A/47/PV.8, at 61, and S.C. Res. 780 (1992)).

¹⁵¹ S.C. Res. 955, U.N. Doc. S/RES/955 (1994).

¹⁵² S.C. Res. 955, U.N. Doc. S/RES/955 (1994).

willing to do so for political reasons.¹⁵³ This is what exactly happening with Nepal's situation, the courts are trying to prosecute the criminals, but the national government is withdrawing charges, giving pardon, promotion etc. "states have preferred to establish courts that are mixed, statute and rules of which are in together govern by international law and domestic law. These types of courts have been set up for Sierra Leone, East Timor, Kosovo and Cambodia."¹⁵⁴

These above-mentioned courts have been established for the reason set forth, which are applicable to the Nepal situation as well.

- During the armed conflict or any disturbance, serious crimes are committed. After the situation is over, it is generally considered that an appropriate reaction to those crimes should not go unpunished, forgetting about them, or in putting in place truth and reconciliation commissions designed to foster national reconciliation process (and to avoid overburdening the local judiciary under reconstruction or reform). Rather, prosecuting those responsible for serious crimes may help in the post-conflict peace-building process may also serve to deter the future commission of large-scale offenses which Nepal has failed to do.
- As we all have seen in the past and in the present times that after the conflict is over, generally everything breaks down, especially the judicial system of the conflict state. This may have happened in situation of East Timor and Sierra Leone, possibly followed by an international conflict as happened in Kosovo. Alternatively, even if a very long time has been elapsed since the crimes were committed, and a stable government has taken a root, as a result of a series of historical factors the judiciary may not be capable of administering justice in an unbiased and even-handed way: this is what happened in Cambodia, where the presence in the government of persons who allegedly are closely linked to the perpetrator of genocide, together with the lack of a really independent judiciary, might lead to unfair trials.¹⁵⁵ As, I have discussed earlier that people with political connection are likely to escape the trial. Situation in Nepal is exactly as similar as what it is in Cambodia.

With above stated reason and past establishment of Ad hoc and Mixed Tribunals for international crimes, United Nation Security Council has an authority to create international tribunal to adjudicate matter of alleged war crimes of Nepalese civil war. As noted, Nepal is not willing to prosecute those responsible for gross violation of human rights. And if state failed to do anything to protect the right of its citizen or failed to provide remedy for violation of their rights, then, it is the utmost duty of United Nation Security Council to prosecute those responsible for international crimes and provide compensation to the victims of crime. Failure of the State and the United Nation Security Council in delivering justice may lead to another conflict because; the victims or families of victims are frustrated because of government unwillingness to do anything. This might lead them to form a group to fight those responsible for war crimes. Nepal is surrounded by the China, India and Pakistan, and it is considered one of the unsafe places because of Naxalites in India, Terrorist in Pakistan, and China's support to the group to fight people to gain power in the region. If justice is not delivered in a timely manner, we might see those individuals forming groups like ISIS, Taliban and others which is very hard to control today.

¹⁵³ <http://cesareromano.com/wp-content/uploads/2015/05/Mixed-crim-tribunals-rev-2-4-7-2010.pdf>

¹⁵⁴ Antonio Cassese, *International Criminal Law* 343 (2d ed. 2003) (discussing the establishment of mixed or special courts in Cambodia, East Timor, Sierra Leone, and Kosovo).

¹⁵⁵ Id. at 344.

V. Continuing Transitional Justice Challenges (2020–2025)

Despite legislative attempts to reform Nepal’s transitional justice framework, systemic barriers continue to prevent meaningful accountability. Between 2020 and 2025, neither the Truth and Reconciliation Commission (TRC) nor the Commission of Investigation on Enforced Disappeared Persons (CIEDP) produced a single completed investigation, forwarded any case for prosecution, or provided comprehensive reparations to victims of serious violations. In its 2023 review, the International Commission of Jurists emphasized that the transitional justice bills proposed from 2022 onward failed to incorporate Supreme Court directives requiring criminal accountability for grave crimes, rendering the legislative approach “incompatible with Nepal’s obligations under international human rights law.”¹⁵⁶

Political parties continued to dominate appointment processes, undermining the independence of newly formed commissions. In June 2025, the government appointed a new TRC chairperson and commissioners without meaningful consultation with victims’ associations or civil society groups, drawing criticism from the UN Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights for reinforcing patterns of “political capture of transitional justice institutions.”¹⁵⁷ The absence of approved regulations and a finalized organizational structure further stalled operational progress, leaving victims uncertain whether their long-delayed claims would ever be addressed.

The broader landscape of accountability in Nepal also remains unchanged. TRIAL International reported in 2023 that conflict-era cases, including emblematic cases such as the Maina Sunuwar torture and killing remain stalled due to the Nepal Army’s refusal to cooperate with civilian courts.¹⁵⁸ This refusal persists despite multiple Supreme Court directives, demonstrating not only institutional resistance but also the state’s inability to enforce judicial orders against powerful security institutions.

The United Nations Human Rights Committee in its 2020 Concluding Observations expressed serious concern that Nepal’s failure to ensure effective investigations and prosecutions constitutes an ongoing breach of Articles 2, 6, 7, and 9 of the ICCPR.¹⁵⁹ The Committee further reiterated that amnesties for torture, enforced disappearance, and extrajudicial killings are impermissible under international law. These concerns were echoed by the Special Rapporteur on truth, justice, and reparation in a 2022 communication, warning that Nepal’s transitional justice process risks “collapsing entirely unless grounded firmly in international legal standards and free from political interference.”¹⁶⁰

Collectively, these developments demonstrate that Nepal’s transitional justice process remains structurally incapable of delivering truth, justice, or reparations. The persistent legislative shortcomings, political interference, security force non-cooperation, and administrative stagnation justify the argument that Nepal continues to be “unable or unwilling” to prosecute serious international crimes—meeting the threshold used in

¹⁵⁶Int’l Comm’n of Jurists, *Nepal: Transitional Justice Bill Fails to Meet International Standards* (Aug. 25, 2023), <https://www.icj.org/nepal-transitional-justice-bill-2023-analysis/>

¹⁵⁷Press Release, Office of the U.N. High Commissioner for Human Rights, *Nepal: Appointment of TRC Commissioners Must Respect Victim Participation* (June 2025), <https://www.ohchr.org>

¹⁵⁸ TRIAL Int’l, *Maina Sunuwar Case Update* (2023), <https://trialinternational.org/latest-updates/nepal/>

¹⁵⁹Human Rights Comm., *Concluding Observations on Nepal*, ¶¶ 11–14, U.N. Doc. CCPR/C/NPL/CO/2 (2020).

¹⁶⁰ Special Rapporteur on the Promotion of Truth, Justice, Reparation and Guarantees of Non-Recurrence, *Communication to the Government of Nepal* (2022), <https://www.ohchr.org>

international criminal law to justify external intervention, including the establishment of a hybrid or fully international tribunal.

VI. Conclusion

Nearly two decades after the end of the armed conflict, Nepal continues to face profound structural failures in delivering truth, justice, and redress to the thousands of victims who endured torture, enforced disappearance, extrajudicial killing, sexual violence, and other serious violations of international human rights and humanitarian law. Although Nepal has repeatedly committed itself through the Comprehensive Peace Agreement, its Constitution, numerous Supreme Court judgments, and international treaty obligations to ensuring accountability for conflict-era violations, these commitments have not translated into meaningful action. The Truth and Reconciliation Commission (TRC) and the Commission of Investigation on Enforced Disappeared Persons (CIEDP) have, across multiple reconstitutions, failed to complete a single full investigation or recommend criminal prosecution for any perpetrator.¹⁶¹ Political interference, security sector non-cooperation, and legislative deficiencies remain entrenched, demonstrating that Nepal's domestic mechanisms are fundamentally incapable of delivering independent, impartial, and victim-centered justice.¹⁶²

Nepal's obligations under international law affirm that serious violations including torture, enforced disappearance, war crimes, and crimes against humanity require effective investigation, prosecution, and remedy.¹⁶³ These duties flow from binding treaties such as the ICCPR and customary international law, and they prohibit granting amnesty for grave crimes.¹⁶⁴ However, legislative proposals introduced between 2022 and 2024 continue to allow amnesties for violations that may constitute international crimes, drawing strong criticism from the United Nations, the International Commission of Jurists, and Amnesty International.¹⁶⁵ As of 2025, the newly appointed TRC commissioners remain unable to function due to a lack of regulations, staffing, and political independence, further eroding public confidence in Nepal's transitional justice process.¹⁶⁶

Given this persistent and well-documented pattern, marked by an inability and unwillingness to prosecute conflict-era crimes, Nepal satisfies the threshold identified in international criminal jurisprudence for external accountability mechanisms. This threshold, articulated by international courts and reflected in the practice of the United Nations Security Council (UNSC), holds that when a State is demonstrably unable or unwilling to prosecute serious international crimes, international intervention may be necessary to protect victims' rights and uphold global justice norms.¹⁶⁷ The experience of the International Criminal Tribunal for the former Yugoslavia (ICTY), the International Criminal Tribunal for Rwanda (ICTR), and

¹⁶¹ Human Rights Watch, *Nepal: Impunity Reigns, Fueling New Rights Violations* (Jan. 12, 2023), <https://www.hrw.org/news/2023/01/12/nepal-impunity-reigns-fueling-new-rights-violations><https://www.hrw.org/news/2023/02/03/nepal-justice-remains-elusive-17-years-after-conflict-ends>

¹⁶² Int'l Comm'n of Jurists, *Nepal: Transitional Justice Bill Needs to Protect Victims, Not Abusers* (Mar. 23, 2023), <https://www.icj.org/nepal-transitional-justice-bill-needs-to-protect-victims-not-abusers/>

¹⁶³ International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights arts. 2, 6–7, Dec. 16, 1966, 999 U.N.T.S. 171.

¹⁶⁴ Human Rights Comm., General Comment No. 31, ¶¶ 15–18, U.N. Doc. CCPR/C/21/Rev.1/Add.13 (2004).

¹⁶⁵ Amnesty International, *Nepal: Transitional Justice Bill Needs to Protect Victims, Not Abusers* (Mar. 24, 2023), <https://www.amnesty.org/en/documents/asa31/6588/2023/en/>

¹⁶⁶ Press Release, Office of the U.N. High Commissioner for Human Rights, *Nepal: Appointment of TRC Commissioners Must Respect Victim Participation* (June 2025), <https://www.ohchr.org>

¹⁶⁷ Prosecutor v. Tadić, Case No. IT-94-1-A, Judgment, 58 (Int'l Crim. Trib. for the Former Yugoslavia July 15, 1999).

hybrid tribunals such as those for Sierra Leone and Cambodia illustrate the international community's responsibility to act when impunity threatens peace, security, and fundamental human rights.

For these reasons, this paper concludes that the UNSC should seriously consider establishing a hybrid or fully international tribunal for Nepal. Such a mechanism would not undermine Nepal's sovereignty; rather, it would reinforce the rule of law, fill institutional gaps, and restore victims' faith in justice.¹⁶⁸ In the absence of credible domestic accountability, international intervention remains the most viable path to ensuring justice for the grave crimes committed during Nepal's armed conflict. Without decisive action, either domestically or internationally, the cycle of impunity will persist, undermining democratic consolidation and leaving victims without truth, accountability, or closure.

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